

Kinetic study of redox reaction between diphenylbenzidine and arsenic(III) oxide

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Abstract : The redox reaction between diphenylbenzidine and arsenic(III) oxide was investigated by using UV visible spectrophotometer. The effect of pH and temperature on the rate of reaction is also being reported. The reaction was carried out between a pH range of 3.0 to 4.5 and at temperatures between 15 to 30 °C. Diphenylbenzidine was prepared through the interaction between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate with a ratio of 1 : 2. Effect of pH and temperature on the order of reaction with respect to each of the reactants i.e. arsenic(III) oxide, diphenylbenzidine and H⁺ was evaluated and found to be first.

The following rate law is recommended :

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 \left\{ \frac{[\text{DPBD}]_T}{1 + K[\text{H}^+]} \right\} [\text{As}_2\text{O}_3]$$

where k_1 is the rate constant for the reaction $[\text{DPBD}] + [\text{As}_2\text{O}_3] \rightarrow \text{product}$, having the value of $k_1 = 2.308 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Activation parameters (E_a , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger) were established. Plot of $\log k$ against $1/T$ was used to determine the value of activation energy with the help of Arrhenius equation, which was found to be $22.06 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger were calculated by plotting $\ln(k/T)$ against inverse temperature ($1/T$). By the slope and intercept of Eyring equation ΔS^\ddagger has been found to be $-0.135 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and that ΔH^\ddagger was $18.744 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Keywords : Redox reactions, diphenylbenzidine, arsenic(III) oxide, absorption coefficient.

Arsenic is not found in nature as a free element. It exhibits a broad range of chemical reactivity with ability to form alloys with other elements. It is a ubiquitous element being widely distributed in the earth. Nature itself is an adequate source of arsenic. Trace quantity of arsenic is also found in most of the fruits, vegetables, fishes and meat, but high level of arsenic lies in seawater. It means that human beings are receiving some amount of arsenic through food, air and drinks every day. Usually a man can receive arsenic up to 150 microgram per kilogram weight of his body without any effect. But a sensitive man may fall sick for having 20 μg arsenic¹.

Arsenic trioxide has shown substantial efficacy in treating both newly diagnosed and relapsed patients with acute promyelocytic leukemia. This success has promoted investigation to elucidate the mechanisms of action underlying such clinical responses². Arsenic trioxide has been proposed as an alternative to treatment with ATRA because it can induce complete remission in both RA-sensitive and RA-resistant APL patients³. The oxidation state of arsenic is reported to influence the signaling pathways that are activated. The pathways that are activated may vary depending on tissue-specific origins or characteristics of particular

cells⁴. Arsenic disturbs natural oxidation and reduction equilibria through various mechanisms involved in complex redox reaction with endogenous oxidants and cellular antioxidant⁵.

Table 1. Values of k_{obs} by plotting a graph between $\ln A_\infty - A_0/A_\infty - A_t$ vs time at four different ratios of diphenylbenzidine and arsenic(III) oxide = $3.33 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol/dm}^3$, pH = 3.0–4.5, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 570 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 4920 \text{ dm}^3/\text{mol cm}$, $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$

Sl. no.	pH	[DPBD] (mol/dm^3)			
		$k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^2$			
1.	3.0	0.640	0.720	11.40	12.00
2.	3.5	0.780	10.90	12.90	13.70
3.	4.0	10.40	23.20	25.90	29.60
4.	4.5	18.70	24.50	28.60	33.10

Arsenic(III) oxide participates readily in oxidation-reduction methylation-demethylation and acid base reactions. Arsenic toxicity in guar gum by the electroanalysis has been studied by Sharma, Rawat and Vyas⁶. The Miller,

Schipper and Waxman have discussed mechanism of action of arsenic(III) oxide⁷. Ghosh, *et al.* have worked on the arsenic chemistry in ground water in the Bengal delta Plain and its implications in agricultural systems⁸. Several other investigations have been reported which involve the kinetics and activation parameters⁹⁻¹⁷.

Table 2. Values of rate for second order of reaction by plotting k_{obs} vs [DPBD] at specific pH, [arsenic(III) oxide] = 3.33×10^{-6} mol/dm³

Sl no.	[Diphenylbenzidine] × 10 ⁵ (mol/dm ³)	k_{obs} (s ⁻¹) × 10 ²	k' (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
At pH 3.5 :			
1.	3.33	0.640	103.26
2.	5.0	0.720	
3.	6.66	11.40	
4.	8.33	12.00	
At pH 4.0 :			
1.	3.33	0.780	124.74
2.	5.0	10.90	
3.	6.66	12.90	
4.	8.33	13.70	
At pH 4.5 :			
1.	3.33	10.40	252.74
2.	5.0	23.20	
3.	6.66	25.90	
4.	8.33	29.60	
At pH 5.0 :			
1.	3.33	18.70	289.48
2.	5.0	24.50	
3.	6.66	28.60	
4.	8.33	33.10	

The present work has been undertaken to perform kinetic investigations for establishing the mechanism of the reaction between arsenic(III) oxide and DPBD.

Table 3. Results of effect of H⁺ ion concentration on rate of reaction k' vs [H⁺]

[As₂O₃] = 3.33×10^{-6} mol/dm³, λ_{max} = 570 nm, ϵ = 4920 dm³/mol cm

Sl. no.	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	k' (dm ³ /mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
1	3.162	103.26
2	1.00	124.74
3.	0.316	252.74
4.	0.1	289.48

Table 4. Values of k_{obs} for four different ratios of DPBD and arsenic trioxide = 3.33×10^{-6} mol/dm³, T = (15, 20, 25 and at 30 °C), λ_{max} = 570 nm, ϵ = 4920 dm³/mol cm

Sl. no.	T (K)	[DPBD] 3.33×10^{-5} (mol/dm ³) $k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^2$	[DPBD] 5.0×10^{-5} (mol/dm ³) $k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^2$	[DPBD] 6.66×10^{-5} (mol/dm ³) $k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^2$	[DPBD] 8.33×10^{-5} (mol/dm ³) $k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1} \times 10^2$
1	288	0.920	17.20	20.40	22.10
2	293	13.40	19.00	21.90	24.00
3.	298	16.10	22.00	23.00	29.00
4.	303	22.90	23.10	29.10	36.30

Table 5. Values of rate constant for second order of reaction by plotting k_{obs} vs [DPBD] at specific pH = 4.0, [As₂O₃] = 3.33×10^{-6} mol/dm³

Sl. no.	[DPBD] × 10 ⁵ (mol/dm ³)	k_{obs} (s ⁻¹) × 10 ³	k' (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
At 15 °C :			
1.	3.33	0.920	194.15
2.	5.0	17.20	
3.	6.66	20.40	
4.	8.33	22.10	
At 20 °C :			
1.	3.33	13.40	218.81
2.	5.0	19.00	
3.	6.66	21.90	
4.	8.33	24.80	
At 25 °C :			
1.	3.33	16.10	248.30
2.	5.0	22.00	
3.	6.66	23.00	
4.	8.33	29.00	
At 30 °C :			
1.	3.33	22.90	305.93
2.	5.0	23.10	
3.	6.66	29.10	
4.	8.33	36.30	

Experimental

All the chemicals used for the study were of AnalaR grade. Diphenylbenzidine (DPBD) was prepared by mixing diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate solution in a ratio of 1 : 2. 0.5 mol/dm³ stock solution of sodium hydroxide was prepared. pH meter of combined glass Ag/AgCl electrode HII-1332 was used for pH measurement. Ionic strength of the reaction mixture was maintained by adding appropriate aliquots of a 0.4 mol/dm³ stock solution of sodium sulfate. The stock solution of diphenylamine was prepared, at a concentration of 0.1 mol/dm³, by dissolving an appropriate amount in 99% methanol. pH was maintained at the required value with the help of sodium hydroxide (NaOH 0.5 mol/dm³). pH meter was used to validate the pH value. 0.1 mol/dm³ cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate stock solution was prepared in 0.5 mol/dm³ H₂SO₄. The pH of cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate was maintained to a required value with the help of sodium hydroxide (0.5 mol/dm³).

Investigation of molar ratio between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate :

Molar ratio between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate was established through spectral analysis. The concentration of diphenylamine was kept constant (2×10^{-4} mol/dm³) and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate (1×10^{-4} , 2×10^{-4} and 3×10^{-4} mol/dm³) was varied in a ratio of 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 and that 1 : 2 ratio was found appropriate.

Molar absorption coefficient of diphenylbenzidine was determined at 570 nm. This was established by obtaining a working curve of absorbance as a function of concentra-

tions of diphenylbenzidine. Molar absorptivity (ϵ) was determined by recording absorbance of solutions having concentrations of 2×10^{-4} , 3×10^{-4} , 4×10^{-4} and 5×10^{-4} mol/dm³ at 570 nm respectively. It was found to be 4920 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Determination of the stability of diphenylbenzidine :

The reaction between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate with a ratio of 1 : 2 was followed spectrophotometrically at the wavelength maxima of (570 nm) of the diphenylbenzidine. The stability of diphenylbenzidine was studied at room temperature by varying the pH between 3.0–4.5. The data was collected with an interval of 1 min until the reaction between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate got completed. Reaction mixture of diphenylbenzidine is stable for 10 min after its formation at pH 4.0.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH : The redox reaction was carried out under the pseudo first-order conditions having diphenylbenzidine > arsenic acid. Kinetic data was collected using integration method by plotting $\ln A_{\infty} - A_0/A_{\infty} - A_t$ vs time, where A_{∞} stands for absorbance at infinite dilution, A_0 and A_t represent initial absorbance and absorbance at time t (s) as shown in Table 1. The plots obtained for constant concentration of arsenic(III) oxide and varying concentration of diphenylbenzidine pertaining to all four ratios (1 : 10, 1 : 15, 1 : 20 and 1 : 25) at pH from 3.0–4.5 produced a straight line passing through the origin. These plots indicate that the reaction is first-order in arsenic trioxide.

Effect of diphenylbenzidine on reaction : The plot of $\ln A_{\infty} - A_0/A_{\infty} - A_t$ vs time, for different pH values helped to compute k_{obs} for each set of experiments. When these values of k_{obs} for different sets, were plotted as a function of concentration of diphenylbenzidine, a straight line was obtained which passed through the origin. From the slope of this, the value of rate constant for second order was calculated. The order of reaction with respect to diphenylbenzidine was also found to be the first. Thus, the overall order of the redox reaction between diphenylbenzidine and arsenic(III) oxide is two.

Kinetic runs were carried out at different pH values. Other conditions remaining same. Rate decreases with pH. Table 3 records the rate constant values for pH variation. The plot of $1/k'$ vs $[H^+]$ (pH ~3.0–4.5) produced straight line with positive slope.

Energy of activation for the system between DPBD and arsenic(III) oxide was determined by plotting a graph between $\log k'$ vs $1/T$ using Arrhenius equation

$$\log k' = -E_a/2.303RT + \log A$$

and was found to be 22.06 kJ mol⁻¹. Eyring equation was applied to determine the enthalpy and entropy of activation. For this $\ln k'/T$ was plotted against inverse temperature.

$$\ln k' = \ln (kT/h) + \Delta S^\ddagger/R - \Delta H^\ddagger/RT$$

These plots produced the values of $\Delta S^\ddagger = -0.135$ kJ mol⁻¹ and the value of ΔH^\ddagger as 18.74 kJ mol⁻¹.

Mechanism :

The mechanism is suggested to incorporate the following three steps

$$K = \frac{[HDPBD]}{[DPBD]_F [H^+]} \quad (4)$$

The rate of the reaction is expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [DPBD]_F [As_2O_3] \quad (5)$$

$$[DPBD]_T = [DPBD]_F - [HDPBD] \quad (6)$$

By rearranging eq. (6)

$$[DPBD]_T - [DPBD]_F = [HDPBD] \quad (7)$$

and then putting value of [HDPBD] from eq. (7) into (4)

$$K = \frac{[DPBD]_T - [DPBD]_F}{[DPBD]_F [H^+]} \quad (8)$$

$$K [H^+] = \frac{[DPBD]_T - [DPBD]_F}{[DPBD]_F}$$

$$K [H^+] = \frac{[DPBD]_T}{[DPBD]_F} - 1$$

$$K [H^+] + 1 = \frac{[DPBD]_T}{[DPBD]_F}$$

$$[DPBD]_F = \frac{[DPBD]_T}{1 + K [H^+]}$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 \left[\frac{[DPBD]_T}{1 + K [H^+]} \right] [As_2O_3] \quad (9)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_1 \frac{[DPBD]_T}{1 + K [H^+]} \quad (10)$$

$$k' = \frac{k_1}{1 + K [H^+]} \quad (11)$$

by taking a reciprocal of eq. (11)

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{K [H^+]}{k_1} \quad (12)$$

for these suggestions to be valid the plot of $1/k'$ vs $[H^+]$ is to be linear if all other factors were kept constant and that

our plots agree to these proposals. The value for second order rate constant k_1 were calculated from the slope and was found to be $k_1 = 2.308 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Conclusion :

Studies pertaining to the mechanism of an oxidation-reduction reaction are focused on information related to atoms/groups or electron transfer. Identifying the atoms that are transferred and how many electrons are transferred. Intermediates, stable or unstable, that are formed during the course of action also get pin pointed accordingly. The mechanism of reaction between DPBD and arsenic(III) oxide has been established, and the rate data is being reported. Rate of the reaction gets decreased with the increase in the $[\text{H}^+]$ at pH 3.0 to 4.5.

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